

Desarrollo de un proyecto divulgativo interactivo
para la formación en la documentación del
contenido audiovisual.

TFG del grado en Gestión de Información y
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Slider de Elementor con carrusel de tarjetas - página del código

<https://makedreamwebsite.com/elementor-advanced-slider-with-card-carousel/>

Fragmento de código CSS del widget Carrusel de testimonios:

```
selector{
  --radius: 8px;
  --height: 320px;
  --active-height: 410px;
  --overlay: 0.75;
}
selector{
  opacity: 0;
  transform: translateX(100px);
  transition: all 0.8s ease-in-out;
}
selector.loaded{
  opacity: 1;
  transform: translateX(0);
}

selector .swiper-wrapper{
  height: var(--active-height);
  align-items: center;
}
selector:not(.loaded) .swiper-wrapper{
  transition-duration: 0s !important;
}
selector .swiper-slide{
  display: flex;
```

```
align-items: flex-end;
border-radius: var(--radius);
height: var(--height);
box-shadow: 0 0 50px rgba(0,0,0,0.15);
}
selector.loaded .swiper-slide{
  transition: all 0.3s ease-in-out 0.2s;
}
selector .swiper-slide.swiper-slide-active{
  height: var(--active-height);
}
selector .swiper-slide:before{
  content: "";
  position: absolute;
  top: 0;
  left: 0;
  background: rgb(0,0,0);
  background: linear-gradient(20deg, rgba(0,0,0,var(--overlay))
0%, rgba(0,0,0,0) 100%);
  height: 100%;
  width: 100%;
  z-index: 1;
}
selector .elementor-testimonial__footer{
  display: block;
}
selector img{
  position: absolute;
  top: 0;
  left: 0;
  width: 100%;
  height: 100%;
  border-radius: var(--radius);
}
selector .elementor-testimonial__cite{
  z-index: 2;
  position: relative;
}
selector .elementor-testimonial__name{
  margin-bottom: 5px;
}
selector .swiper-pagination,
selector .elementor-swiper-button{
  display: none;
}
selector .swiper-container{
```

```
    overflow: hidden;
    margin-left: auto;
    margin-right: auto;
}

@media (max-width: 1024px){
selector{
    --height: 180px;
    --active-height: 250px;
}
}

@media (max-width: 767px){
selector{
    --height: 80px;
    --active-height: 105px;
    width: 100% !important;
    max-width: var(--container-widget-width, 300px) !important;
}
selector .elementor-testimonial__cite{
    opacity: 0;
}
}
```

Fragmento de código JavaScript para control deslizante avanzado:

```
<script src="https://code.jquery.com/jquery-3.6.0.min.js"></script>

<script>

var $ = jQuery

$(document).ready(function(){

$('.as-slider').each(function(){

var $this = $(this),
    currentSlide = 0,
    previousSlide = 0,
    slideNumber = $this.find('.as-side-slider .swiper-slide:not(.swiper-slide-duplicate)').length,
    barHTML = '',
    forward,
    textContainer = $this.find('.as-changing-widget')

for(var i=0; i<slideNumber;i++){

    barHTML += `<span class="dot"><span class="dot-number">${i+1}</span></span>`
}

$this.find('.as-bar .dot').remove()
$this.find('.as-bar').append(barHTML)
$this.find('.as-bar .dot').eq(0).addClass('active')

textContainer.each(function(){
    var texts = $(this).find('.elementor-widget').eq(0)
    texts.addClass('currentUp')
    $(this).css('--h', texts.height()+ 'px')
})

setTimeout(function(){
    $this.addClass('loaded')
    if($this.find('.as-side-slider .swiper-container-initialized, .as-side-slider .swiper-initialized').length){
        $this.find('.as-side-slider').addClass('loaded')
    }

    var init = setInterval(function(){
        if($this.find('.as-side-slider .swiper-container-initialized, .as-side-slider .swiper-initialized').length){

            $this.find('.as-side-slider').addClass('loaded')
            clearInterval(init)
        }
    }, 50)
}, 500)
```

```

var bgs = JSON.parse($this.attr('data-
settings')).background_slideshow_gallery,
    bgHTML = '<div class="as-slider-background">'

if(bgs){
    bgs.forEach(function(background){
        bgHTML += ``
    })
}
bgHTML += '</div>'

$this.find('.as-slider-background').remove()
$this.prepend(bgHTML)

var backgrounds = $this.find('.as-slider-background img')

backgrounds.eq(0).addClass('currentForward')

setInterval(function(){
    currentSlide = $this.find('.as-side-slider .swiper-slide-
active').attr('data-swiper-slide-index')
    if(previousSlide != currentSlide) {

        if( previousSlide < currentSlide ){
            forward = true
        }
        if( previousSlide > currentSlide ){
            forward = false
        }
        if( previousSlide == slideNumber - 1 && currentSlide == 0
){
            forward = true
        }
        if( previousSlide == 0 && currentSlide == slideNumber - 1
){
            forward = false
        }
        textContainer.each(function(){
            var texts = $(this).find('.elementor-widget')

            $(this).css('--h',
texts.eq(currentSlide).height()+'px')

            texts.removeClass('prev next currentUp currentDown')
            backgrounds.removeClass('prev currentBackward
currentForward')

            backgrounds.eq(previousSlide).addClass('prev')

            if(forward) {
                texts.eq(previousSlide).addClass('prev')
                texts.eq(currentSlide).addClass('currentUp')
            }
        })
    }
}, 5000)

```

```

backgrounds.eq(currentSlide).addClass('currentForward')

        }else{
            texts.eq(previousSlide).addClass('next')
            texts.eq(currentSlide).addClass('currentDown')

backgrounds.eq(currentSlide).addClass('currentBackward')
        }
    })

    $this.find('.as-bar .dot').removeClass('active')
    $this.find('.as-bar
    .dot').eq(currentSlide).addClass('active')
    }
    previousSlide = currentSlide
}, 500)

$this.find('.as-bar .dot').on('click', function(){

    var index = $(this).index()

    $this.find('.as-side-slider .swiper-pagination-
bullet').eq(index).trigger('click')
    $this.find('.as-side-slider .swiper-
container').trigger('mouseleave')

})
$this.find('.as-slider-left').on('click', function(){

    $this.find('.as-side-slider .elementor-swiper-button-
prev').trigger('click')
    $this.find('.as-side-slider .elementor-
swiper').trigger('mouseleave')
})
$this.find('.as-slider-right').on('click', function(){

    $this.find('.as-side-slider .elementor-swiper-button-
next').trigger('click')
    $this.find('.as-side-slider .elementor-
swiper').trigger('mouseleave')
})
$this.find('.as-slider-left a, .as-slider-right a').on('click',
function(e) {

    e.preventDefault()
})

})
})
})

```

```
$(window).on('resize', function(){

$('.as-slider').each(function(){

    var textContainer = $(this).find('.as-changing-widget')

    textContainer.each(function(){
        var texts = $(this).find('.elementor-widget.currentUp,
        .elementor-widget.currentDown')

        $(this).css('--h', texts.height()+'px')
    })
})
})

</script>
```

Fragmento de código CSS para el contenedor de encabezado:

```
selector{
  --speed: 0.8s;
  --gap: 40px;
}
selector{
  transition: all 0.3s ease-in-out;
  height: var(--h);
  --height: calc(var(--h) + var(--gap));
  overflow: hidden !important;
}
selector .elementor-widget{
  position: absolute;
  top: 50%;
  transform: translateY(-50%);
}
selector .elementor-widget > *{
  transform: translateY(calc(-10 * var(--height)));
  transition: none !important;
}
selector .elementor-widget.prev > *{
  animation: prev var(--speed) ease-in-out;
  transform: translateY(calc(-1 * var(--height)));
}
selector .elementor-widget.next > *{
  animation: next var(--speed) ease-in-out;
  transform: translateY(var(--height));
}
selector .elementor-widget.currentUp,
selector .elementor-widget.currentDown{
  z-index: 1;
}
selector .elementor-widget.currentUp > *{
  animation: currentUp var(--speed) ease-in-out;
  transform: translateY(0);
}
selector .elementor-widget.currentDown > *{
  animation: currentDown var(--speed) ease-in-out;
  transform: translateY(0);
}

@keyframes prev {
  0%   {transform: translateY(0);}
  100% {transform: translateY(calc(-1 * var(--height)));}
}
```

```
@keyframes next {  
  0%    {transform: translateY(0);}  
  100%  {transform: translateY(var(--height));}  
}
```

```
@keyframes currentUp {  
  0%    {transform: translateY(var(--height));}  
  100%  {transform: translateY(0);}  
}
```

```
@keyframes currentDown {  
  0%    {transform: translateY(calc(-1 * var(--height)));}  
  100%  {transform: translateY(0);}  
}
```

Fragmento de código CSS para contenedor de párrafo:

```
selector{
  --speed: 0.5s;
  --gap: 40px;
}
selector{
  transition: all 0.3s ease-in-out;
  height: var(--h);
  --height: calc(var(--h) + var(--gap));
  overflow: hidden !important;
}
selector .elementor-widget{
  position: absolute;
  top: 50%;
  transform: translateY(-50%);
}
selector .elementor-widget > *{
  transform: translateY(calc(-10 * var(--height)));
  transition: none !important;
}
selector .elementor-widget.prev > *{
  animation: prev var(--speed) ease-in-out;
  transform: translateY(calc(-1 * var(--height)));
}
selector .elementor-widget.next > *{
  animation: next var(--speed) ease-in-out;
  transform: translateY(var(--height));
}
selector .elementor-widget.currentUp,
selector .elementor-widget.currentDown{
  z-index: 1;
}
selector .elementor-widget.currentUp > *{
  animation: currentUp var(--speed) ease-in-out;
  transform: translateY(0);
}
selector .elementor-widget.currentDown > *{
  animation: currentDown var(--speed) ease-in-out;
  transform: translateY(0);
}

@keyframes prev {
  0%   {transform: translateY(0);}
  100% {transform: translateY(calc(-1 * var(--height)));}
}
```

```
@keyframes next {  
  0%    {transform: translateY(0);}  
  100%  {transform: translateY(var(--height));}  
}
```

```
@keyframes currentUp {  
  0%    {transform: translateY(var(--height));}  
  100%  {transform: translateY(0);}  
}
```

```
@keyframes currentDown {  
  0%    {transform: translateY(calc(-1 * var(--height)));}  
  100%  {transform: translateY(0);}  
}
```

Fragmento de código CSS para el indicador izquierdo (contenedor):

```
selector{
  --dot-size: 23px;
  --line-color: #B0B7D04D;
  --dot-color: #B0B7D0;
  --dot-color-active: #B0B7D0;
  color: #fff;
  font-size: 13px;
  font-weight: bold;
}
selector{
  height: 80vh;
  height: var(--min-height);
  max-height: 80vh;
  min-height: 0 !important;
}
selector .dot{
  height: var(--dot-size);
  width: var(--dot-size);
  background: var(--dot-color);
  border-radius: 100%;
  display: flex;
  align-items: center;
  justify-content: center;
  position: relative;
  transform: scale(0.3);
  transition: all 0.3s ease-in-out;
  cursor: pointer;
}
selector .dot-number{
  opacity: 0;
  transition: all 0.3s ease-in-out;
}
selector .dot.active{
  transform: scale(1);
  background: var(--dot-color-active);
}
selector .dot.active .dot-number{
  opacity: 1;
}
selector:before{
  content: "";
  position: absolute;
  top: 50%;
  height: calc(100% - 20px);
  max-height: 90vh;
```

```
width: 1px;
background: var(--line-color);
left: 50%;
transform: translateX(-50%) translateY(-50%);
}

@media (max-width: 767px){
selector{
transform: translateX(-50%);
flex-wrap: nowrap !important;
}
selector:before {
width: calc(100% - 20px);
height: 1px;

}
}
```

Fragmento de código CSS para el contenedor principal más importante:

```
selector{
  background: #fff;
  --background-speed: 0.5s;
}
selector .elementor-background-slideshow{
  display: none;
}
selector .as-slider-background,
selector .as-slider-background img{
  position: absolute;
  top: 0;
  left: 0;
  width: 100%;
  height: 100%;
  transition: all 1s ease-in-out;
}
selector .as-slider-background img{
  object-fit: cover;
  opacity: 0;
  transform: scale(1.1);
}
selector .as-slider-background img.prev,
selector .as-slider-background img.currentBackward,
selector .as-slider-background img.currentForward{
  opacity: 1;
  transform: scale(1.1);
}

selector .as-slider-background img.currentBackward,
selector .as-slider-background img.currentForward{
  z-index: 1;
  opacity: 1;
  animation: bgNext var(--background-speed) linear;
  transition: all 1s ease-in-out;
  transform: scale(1);
}

selector:before{
  z-index: 2;
}
selector > .elementor-element{
  z-index: 3;
}

selector .as-bar,
```

```

selector .as-slider-left,
selector .as-slider-right{
    opacity: 0;
    transition: all 0.8s ease-in-out;
}
selector.loaded .as-bar,
selector.loaded .as-slider-left,
selector.loaded .as-slider-right{
    opacity: 1;
}
/*selector .ds-slider-left a:focus,*/
/*selector .ds-slider-right a:focus{*/
/*    outline: none !important;*/
/*}*/

@keyframes bgNext {
    0%    {opacity: 0; transform: scale(1.1);}
    100%  {opacity: 1; transform: scale(1);}
}

@media (min-width: 768px){
selector .as-bar,
selector .as-slider-left,
selector .as-slider-right{
    position: relative;
}
}

@media (max-width: 1380px) and (min-width: 768px){
selector{
    padding-left: 4%;
    padding-right: 4%;
}
}

@media (max-width: 767px){
selector .as-slider-left{
    left: calc(50% - 300px/2) !important;
}
selector .as-slider-right{
    right: calc(50% - 300px/2) !important;
}
}

```

Fragmento de código CSS (@media query) para el contenedor principal de (encabezado y texto):

```
@media (max-width: 1750px) and (min-width: 1381px){
selector{
padding-left: 8%;
padding-right: 12%;
}
}
@media (max-width: 1380px) and (min-width: 768px){
selector{
padding-left: 0.5%;
padding-right: 5.5%;
}
}
```